

Implementation of effect biomarkers and implementation of 2nd set priority chemicals in the aligned studies

Additional Deliverable Report

AD8.3

WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

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1 Authors and acknowledgements

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2 Introduction

In 2019 we performed an inquiry about the interest in analysing 2nd set priority substances in the aligned studies. Based on the interest indications that we received from PI's and National Hubs proposals were presented to the MB (see appendix). After approval of the proposals interested partners were allocated (tentative) budgets in AWP2020/2021. Since then WP9 has selected a fixed set of metabolites to be analysed per substance group, identified expert labs and initiated an ICI/EQUAS among these expert labs. Information about required sample volumes and price of the different potential expert labs was provided to the PI's in March 2020. Based on this new recent information PI's were asked to confirm their participation. They were asked to verify if the required sample volume is available and if co-financing is available to implement analysis of 2nd set priority chemicals in their samples.

In collaboration with WP14 a proposal was prepared for the implementation of effect biomarkers in connection to exposure to the 1st set priority substances in the aligned studies. After development of a draft research plan PI's were asked to express their interest in participating and a proof-of-concept was accepted by the MB. The plan was also presented at the consortium meeting in October 2019. After this presentation additional partners expressed their interest and an update of the proposal with additional partners was prepared and presented to the MB in November 2019.

In this Additional Deliverable partners participating in (a) implementing effect biomarkers in connection to 1st set priority chemicals and (b) implementing exposure biomarkers for the second set priority chemicals are confirmed.

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3 Description of Programmed Activities

3.1 Implementation of biomarkers of effect in aligned studies in connection to exposures to 1st set priority chemicals – work description

3.1.1 WP8: Work Package Leader: DH

3.1.1.1 Task 8.1A: Alignment of national studies

Details of the main activities included in the implementation of biomarkers of effect are provided below and will be done in close collaboration with WP8, WP10, WP13 and WP14.

Implementing analysis of effect biomarkers in connection to 1st set priority chemicals in the aligned studies

The implementation of effect biomarkers will involve the use of samples already collected (no new fieldwork will be undertaken).

The participating aligned studies (NIPH, NPHI, JSI, SDU, SZU, ISCI, VITO, EPIUD) will:

- Obtain and demonstrate ethical approval for conducting new analyses of selected biomarkers of effect. This includes preparing and submitting an application (or amendment) to an ethics committee. (0.25PM)
- Make samples available for analysis of selected effect biomarkers. For more detail about which aligned study will analyse which effect biomarkers see Table 1 (children) and Table 2 (teenagers).
- Send their samples to the selected labs (UGR, INSERM, MU) for the analysis of effect biomarkers following the SOP for sample transport developed by WP7.
- In collaboration with Task 10.6, share the individual data of effect markers and accompanying variables in HBM4EU harmonised format. This includes signing all necessary contracts to ensure GDPR compliant exchange of the data into the data platform as established by VITO (task 10.1) and, if legally allowed, into IPCHEM.

Besides new measurements of effect biomarkers, health outcome data available from the aligned studies will be collected to complement the statistical analysis of exposure -effect associations and pathway analysis.

The aligned studies will provide information about the availability of health outcome information of interest for evaluation if harmonisation across studies is possible. VITO, NIPH, EPIUD and KI perform a feasibility check for post-harmonisation of available data on neurodevelopment, asthma/allergy, metabolism/BMI, pubertal development and develop a codebook for these health outcome related variables and confounders. The aligned studies post-harmonise the available health outcome data according to the codebook.

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Table 1: Overview table analysis in children conducted under WP14

Implementation biomarkers of effect in <u>children</u>	MATRIX	Region	North		East		South	
		Study	NEB II	OCC	PCB COHORT	INAIRQ	SLO CRP	NAC II
		Country	NO	DK	SK	HU	SL	IT
		N° samples	300	300	300	264	148	300
		Age (years)	6-11	6-7	10-12	8-11	7-10	6-8
Clinical effect biomarkers (TSH, T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG)	Serum	√ ¹	√	-	-	√	-	
BDNF	serum		-	-	-	√	-	
BDNF	Urine	√	?	√	√	-	√	
Targeted DNA methylation (BDNF)	Whole blood	√	-	-	-	√ ²	-	
Histone modifications (ER, AR, TR)	Whole blood	√	-	-	-	√	-	
Untargeted DNA methylation	Whole blood	A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples.						-
Untargeted histone modifications	Whole blood	A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples.						-

“√” = parameter will be analysed, “-” = parameter will not be analysed.

¹ NIPH: Only a subset of the clinical markers will be assessed, 7 of the 8 clinical parameters: T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, and SHBG (7*25 µL).

² Extracted DNA will be sent for DNA methylation analysis instead of whole blood

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Table 2: Overview table analysis in teenagers conducted under WP14:

Implementation biomarkers of effect in <u>teenagers</u>	MATRIX	Region	North	East	South		West
		Study	NEBII	PCB cohort (follow-up)	SLO CRP	BEA	FLEHS IV
		Country	NO	SK	SL	ES	BE
		N° samples	184	300	98	300	300
		Age (years)	12-14	15-16	12-15	14-16	14-15
Clinical effect biomarkers (LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG, glucose, insulin, TG, TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, leptin, adiponectin, TSH, T3, T4)	Serum		√ ³	√	√	√	√
Kisspeptin	serum		√ ⁴	√	√	√ ⁴	√
8-OHdG	Urine		√	√	√ ⁵	√	√ ⁵
Targeted DNA methylation (Kisspeptin)	Whole blood		√	-	√ ⁶	√	√
Histone modifications (ER, AR, PPARα, PPARγ, GR, TR)	Whole blood		√	-	√	√	√
Untargeted DNA methylation	Whole blood	A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available teenager samples.					
Untargeted histone modifications	Whole blood	A Subset of 20 samples to be selected from the available children samples.					

³ NIPH: Only a subset of the classical biomarkers will be assessed, both in children and teenagers, i.e. 7 of the classical parameters: T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, and SHBG (8*25 uL). As part of another study the other classical biomarkers were measured and these data will be shared. Classical biomarkers and BDNF will be measured in plasma instead of serum.

⁴ ISCIII and NIPH: Kisspeptin will be analysed if sufficient sample volume available.

⁵ JSI and VITO: 8-OHdG data already available and will be shared.

⁶ Extracted DNA will be sent for DNA methylation analysis instead of whole blood

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3.1.2 WP10: Work Package Leader: VITO

3.1.2.1 Task 10.3A: Development of statistical analysis plans and coordination of analysis

VITO will coordinate the update of the statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8 (D10.12) by M50. The statistical analysis plan will be developed in close collaboration with the other partners from the statistical working group (UBA, ANSP, ISGLOBAL), researchers from the 1st set substance groups, CGLs 1st set, and WP13/14 (INSERM, MU, UGR) for the exposure-effects associations and the full path analysis of exposure-effect biomarkers-health outcome data.

3.1.2.2 Task 10.4A: Data analysis including the generation of European reference values (RVs)

For all aligned studies that have data available on the selected health effects, we will look into relevant exposure-effect associations for the 1st set of prioritised substances. That is:

- Phthalates/DINCH and FRs in relation to neurodevelopment in children (EPIUD)
- Phthalates/DINCH and FRs in relation to BMI & metabolism in children (NIPH)
- Phthalates/DINCH in relation to BMI & metabolism in teenagers (NIPH)
- PFASs in relation to BMI & metabolism in teenagers (KI)
- Phthalates/DINCH and PFASs in relation to sexual maturation in teenagers (VITO)
- Phthalates/DINCH and FRs in relation to asthma & allergy in children (VITO)
- Phthalates/DINCH and PFASs in relation to asthma & allergy in teenagers (VITO)

From these statistical analyses results, scientific peer-reviewed publications and policy briefs will be elaborated (in collaboration with WP2 and WP5).

For those aligned studies that have measured/obtained specific effect markers and health effects statistical analysis could be performed to look into the path analysis linking exposure to health effects via established effect biomarkers (linked to WP13 and WP14). The following path analyses will be investigated:

- Phthalates/DINCH and FRs in relation to **neurodevelopment in children**, with molecular and clinical markers as BDNF (UGR, INSERM, EPIUD)

- Phthalates/DINCH and FRs in relation to **BMI & metabolism** in **children**, with available clinical markers as cholesterol, triglycerides (NIPH)

- Phthalates/DINCH in relation to **BMI & metabolism** in **teenagers**, with molecular and clinical markers as kisspeptin (NIPH, UGR, MU, INSERM)
- PFASs in relation to **BMI & metabolism** in **teenagers**, with molecular and clinical markers as kisspeptin (KI, UGR, MU, INSERM)

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- Phthalates/DINCH and PFASs in relation to **sexual maturation in teenagers**, with molecular and clinical markers as kisspeptin (VITO, UGR, INSERM, MU)

From these statistical analyses results, scientific peer-reviewed publications and policy briefs will be initiated (in collaboration with WP2 and WP5), but this work will probably not be finalised by the end of 2021.

Task 10.6A: Integrating co-funded data into HBM4EU repository and IPCHEM

EEA will continue the work with partners of co-funded studies to bring in and integrate metadata and co-funded HBM data for the 1st set and 2nd set of priority substances into IPCHEM. The work of 10.6 will focus on integrating metadata and co-funded:

- Newly measured effect biomarkers and accompanying variables (harmonised individual data) from the aligned studies (Task 8.1) into the data platform established by VITO (Task 10.1) (ISCI, JSI, NIPH, NPHI, SDU, SZU, VITO, EPIUD).
- Health outcome data on neurodevelopment, metabolism or asthma/allergy from the aligned studies in children (Task 8.1) into the data platform established by VITO (Task 10.1) in harmonised individual format (EPIUD, SDU, SZU, NIPH, NPHI, UBA, JSI).
- Health outcome data on sexual maturation, metabolism or asthma/allergy from the aligned studies in teenagers (Task 8.1) into the data platform established by VITO (Task 10.1) in harmonised individual format (ISCI, JSI, NIPH, NFA, SZU, VITO, UBA, MU).

3.1.3 WP14: Work Package Leader: UGR

Task 14.2 Implementation of effect biomarkers for the 1st set of prioritised chemicals in the aligned studies.

- UGR has fine-tuned and validated measurements for selected classic biomarkers, as well as for BDNF in serum and urine samples. BDNF measurement, in both urine and serum samples, has been technically validated. Both serum and urinary BDNF have already been implemented in the INMA-Granada birth cohort as pilot study, in order to complete the QA/QC. The aim of these pilot studies is to assess its physiological validity before BDNF implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies. Kiss measurement has also been technically validated. However, the validation of the assessment of Kisspeptin in serum in

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the INMA-Granada birth cohort, as pilot study, is not finish yet, and needs to be confirmed (The COVID situation has delayed this outcome).

- A contingency plan is contemplated in case of some of the QA/QC do not convince the aligned study owners. Two options are contemplated: samples returning to owners or measurement of another selected effect biomarker after the approval of both MB and study owners.
- Samples from aligned studies have started to arrive to UGR and the first preliminary data will be available at the end of December 2020, beginning of 2021 (samples from FELSH IV, SLO CRP, PCB cohort and PCB cohort (follow-up), BEA study are already at UGR).
- INSERM has also validated the measurement of BDNF and Kisspeptin DNA methylation in blood, as well as the measures for histone modifications for ER, AR, PPAR α , PPAR γ , GR and TR. There has been a methodological change regarding DNA methylation analyses (see in detail below). Accordingly, the corresponding budget recalculations have been made.
- MU has validated the LC-MS/MS methodology to assess urinary 8OHdG concentrations, which is ready to be implemented.

Changes in the methodology for DNA methylation

In the proof-of-concept study conducted on placenta samples from the INMA mother-child and the French PELAGIE cohorts, a DNA methylation analysis technique called High-Resolution Melt (HRM) was applied by INSERM. However, when applied to blood samples, certain drawbacks related to the informativeness of the HRM technique (see below for the description of both methods) were identified. An alternative method called targeted pyrosequencing was then applied to overcome this limitation. Pyrosequencing is broadly used in the scientific community, especially in epidemiological studies for DNA methylation analyses (Chen et al., 2016; Parade et al. 2016). The main advantage is that pyrosequencing provides information on the DNA methylation levels at individual CpGs at a specific region on the gene of interest. The technique is reproducible and provides information on the percentage of methylation at each of the CpG islands measured. HRM, on the contrary, provides only the information on the general methylation levels of DNA without precision of methylation levels at given CpGs.

Quality control: Quality control data is available for pyrosequencing ensuring reliability and robustness of the method. Pyrosequencing machine performs quality control for the conversion of unmethylated cytosine residues during bisulfite treatment and subsequent PCR amplification. Moreover, commercially available control human DNA that is methylated and unmethylated (Qiagen, France) will be used to prepare a standard curve (0%, 10%, 50% and 100% methylated DNA). HPLC-grade water will be used as negative control.

Limitation and Change in Plan of Action: Pyrosequencing is more expensive compared to HRM method. To adhere to the initially proposed budget, the initial list of target gene has been adapted, and certain target genes will be analysed using Pyrosequencing DNA Methylation technique and the remaining target genes will be studied by analysing another epigenetic modification called histone modification. By examining the levels of a histone modification called trimethylation of histone 3 at lysine 4 (H3K4me3) at the promoters of the target genes, information on actively transcribing genes can be obtained. A technique called chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) will be used, which is less expensive compared to pyrosequencing. Moreover, analyses of H3K4me3 mark at the promoters of target genes of interest helps to identify their transcription status whereas DNA methylation analyses gives information only about the methylation levels of the target genes. Both these techniques (pyrosequencing for DNA methylation analyses and ChIP technique to

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study histone H3K4me3 modifications) have been successfully applied to 119 blood samples from the INMA Granada boys' cohort.

Target genes to be analysed by pyrosequencing and histone modifications: BDNF and KISS1 targets will be analysed using the pyrosequencing technique to study their DNA methylation levels. It must be noted that these targets cannot be studied using H3K4me3 histone modification technique because ChIP primers cannot be designed for these two genes due to absence of H3K4me3 peaks in blood cells. The remaining target genes, ER, AR, TR, GR, PPARA, PPARG will be analysed by using H3K4me3 chromatin immunoprecipitation method.

New Budget for Pyrosequencing and Chromatin Immunoprecipitation techniques: To adhere to the initially proposed budget, certain target genes will be analysed using Pyrosequencing DNA Methylation technique and the remaining target genes will be studied by analysing another epigenetic modification called histone modification. There would be no change in the amount of DNA/ volume of blood required for the entire analyses. It would remain the same as previously communicated to the participating aligned study partners.

a) DNA Methylation by pyrosequencing

Table 3: Children's Cohort- Budget* needed for DNA methylation of BDNF

Cohort	Slovenia Children Cohort –JSI	Norway Children Cohort- NIPH
Sample Nos.	148 samples	300 Samples
Step 1: DNA extraction and Bisulfite conversion (7 €= 3.50 € for DNA extraction and 3.50 € for bisulfite conversion/ sample) DNA extraction price would not be applied if extracted DNA is provided (i.e., JSI send DNA extracts).	148 x 3.50 = 518.00 €	300 x 7= 2,100.00 €
Step 2: PCR amplification & purification for BDNF/ sample (3 €).	148 x 3 = 444.00 €	300 x 3 = 900.00 €
Step 3: Pyrosequencing (20 € per sample/ target).	148 x 20 = 2,960.00 €	300 x 20 = 6,000.00 €
Total cost per cohort (in €)	3,922.00 €	9,000.00 €

*Study partners will contribute to 30% of the price indicated for their corresponding cohort

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Table 4: Teenager's Cohort- Budget* needed for DNA methylation of *KISS1*

Cohort	Slovenia Teenager Cohort-JSI	Belgium Teenager Cohort-VITO	Norway Teenager Cohort-NIPH
Sample Nos.	98 samples	294 samples	184 samples
Step 1: DNA extraction and Bisulfite conversion (7 € (3.50 € for DNA extraction and 3,50 € for bisulfite conversion)/ sample) DNA extraction price would not apply if extracted DNA is provided	98 x 3.50= 343.00 €	294 x 7= 2,058.00 €	184 x 7= 1,288.00 €
Step 2: PCR amplification & purification for <i>KISS1</i> target/ sample (3 €).	98 x 3= 294.00 €	294 x 3= 882.00 €	184 x 3=552.00 €
Step 3: Pyrosequencing (20 € per sample/ target <i>KISS1</i>).	98 x 20=1,960.00 €	294 x 20= 5,880.00 €	184 x 20=3,680.00 €
Total cost per cohort (in €)	2,597.00 €	8,820.00 €	5,520.00 €

*Study partners will contribute to 30% of the price indicated for their corresponding cohort

Grand total for DNA methylation (BDNF + Kisspeptin) for all the cohorts (in €): **29,859 €**

b) Chromatin Immunoprecipitation (ChIP) for histone modifications

Table 5: Children's Cohort- Price Calculations*

Cohort	Slovenia Children Cohort -JSI	Norway Children Cohort-NIPH
Sample Nos.	148 samples	300 Samples
Step 1: Chromatin immunoprecipitation using H3K4me3 antibody and Dynabeads. These are the most expensive products that are used for this experiment.		
Antibody H3K4me3 (4.31 € per sample)	4.31 x 148 samples =637.88 €	4.31 x 300 samples =1,293.00 €
Dynabeads (3.42 € per sample)	3.42 x 148 samples = 506.16 €	3.42 x 300 samples = 1,026.00 €
Step 2: Targeted ChIP-qPCR (for ER, AR, TR in children)		
SyberGreen Dye (0.305 € per sample/ target)	148 x 0.305 x 3 target (TR)= 135.42 €	300 x 0.305 x 3 target (TR)= 274.50 €
Common solutions for ChIP/ Buffers 1000 € in total for 1024 samples. So approximately 1 euro per sample	148.00 €	300.00 €
Total cost per cohort (in €)	1,427.46 €	2,893.50 €

*Study partners will contribute to 30% of the price indicated for their corresponding cohort

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Table 6: Teenager's Cohort- Price Calculations*

Cohort	Slovenia Teenager Cohort-JSI	Belgium Teenager Cohort-VITO	Norway Teenager Cohort-NIPH
Sample Nos.	98 samples	294 samples	184 samples
Step 1: Chromatin immunoprecipitation using H3K4me3 antibody and Dynabeads. These are the most expensive products that are used for this experiment.			
Antibody H3K4me3 (4.31 € per sample)	4.31 x 98 samples =422.38 €	4.31 x 294 samples =1,267,14 €	4.31 x 184 samples =793.04 €
Dynabeads (3.42 € per sample)	3.42 x 98 samples = 335.16 €	3.42 x 294 samples = 1,005.48 €	3.42 x 184 samples = 629.28 €
Step 2: Targeted ChIP-qPCR (ER, AR, PPARG, PPARA, GR, TR in Teenagers) 6 target genes:			
SyberGreen Dye (0.305 € per sample/ target)	98 x 0.305 x 6 targets= 179.34 €	294 x 0.305 x 6 targets= 538.02 €	184 x 0.305 x 6 targets= 336.72 €
Common solutions for ChIP/ Buffers 1000 € in total for 1024 samples. So approximately 1 euro per sample	98.00 €	294.00 €	184.00 €
Total cost per cohort (in €)	1,034.88 €	3,104.64 €	1,943.04 €

*Study partners will contribute to 30% of the price indicated for their corresponding cohort

Grand total for histone modifications for all the cohorts (in €): **10,403.52 €**

Grand total for all the epigenetic studies (Pyrosequencing + ChIP): **40,262.52 €**

70% of the cost covered by HBM4EU: **27,992.468 €**

30% of the cost covered by Study Partners: **11,996.772 €**

Summary:

- The molecular markers to be studied for DNA methylation using pyrosequencing technique: BDNF in children and KISS1 in Teenagers
- The molecular markers to be studied for histone H3K4me3 modifications using Chromatin Immunoprecipitation (ChIP) technique: ER, AR and TR in children and ER, AR, PPARG, PPARA, GR, TR in Teenagers

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3.2 Implementation of 2nd set priority chemicals in aligned studies – work description

3.2.1 WP8: Work Package Leader: DH

Task 8.1A: Alignment of national studies

Details of the main activities included in the implementation of (a) the second set of priority chemicals are provided below and will be done in close collaboration with WP8, WP10, WP13 and WP14.

Task 14.2 Implementation of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of prioritised chemicals in the aligned studies.

The implementation of second set priority chemicals will involve the use of samples already collected (**no new fieldwork will be undertaken**).

The participating aligned studies (NIPH, NFA, UI, RegionH, NIOM, EPIUD, JSI, ISCI, INSA, UBA, LNS, SWISS TPH, ANSP, VITO, PIH, RIVM, MOH-IL, MOH-CY) will:

- Obtain and demonstrate ethical approval for conducting new chemical analysis (second set priority substances). This includes preparing and submitting an application (or amendment) to an ethics committee.
- Make samples available for analysis of second set priority chemicals. For more detail about which aligned study will analyse which second set priority chemicals see Table , Table , Table .
- Transfer of the aligned studies samples to a HBM4EU qualified expert lab for the analysis following the SOP for sample transport developed by WP7.
- The aligned studies which already have second set priority data available and agreed to share the data with HBM4EU will perform a-posteriori quality control of analysis organised by WP9.
- Post-harmonise additional questionnaire data which is relevant for exposure to second set priority chemicals. This includes providing detailed input about their questionnaire and harmonising their data according to the HBM4EU developed codebook (M43).
- In collaboration with Task 10.6, share the individual data in HBM4EU harmonised format by the end of M48. This includes signing all necessary contracts to ensure GDPR compliant exchange of the harmonised individual data into the data platform as established by VITO (task 10.1). And making metadata and harmonised aggregated data accessible through IPCHEM for HBM4EU consortium members and EU commission and agencies and EU national bodies.

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Table 7: Metabolites selected by WP9 per substance group to be analysed by selected expert labs

Pesticides:
3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy)
cis-(2,2-dibromovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid (cis-DBCA)
cis-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (cis-DCCA)
trans-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (trans-DCCA)
3-PBA
4-fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid (4-F-3-PBA)
cis-3-(2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid (CIF3CA)
Glyphosate
Aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA)
Acrylamide:
N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoyl-ethyl)cysteine (AAMA)
N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl)cysteine (GAMA)
Arsenic:
Arsenic (total)
As (III)
As (V)
Monomethylarsonic acid (MMA)
Dimethylarsinic acid (DMA)
Arsenobetaine
UV-filters:
2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone (BP1)
2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone (BP3)
Mycotoxins:
Deoxynivalenol (total)

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Table 8: Studies implementing second set priority chemicals in children.

CHILDREN										
	North	East	South			West				Other
	NEBII	POLAES	SLO CRP	NAC II	Organiko	ESTEBAN	GerES V	3xG	Dutch SPECIMEn (control)	RAV MABAT
	Norway	Poland	Slovenia	Italy	Cyprus	France	Germany	Belgium	The Netherlands	Israel
	NIPH	NIOM	JSI	EPIUD	MOH-CY	ANSP	UBA	VITO/PIH	RIVM	MOH-IL
	300	300	149	300	180	300	300	150	103	103
Pesticides (chlorpyrifos/Pyrethroids) in urine	√	-	(√) TCPy, 3PBA, 4F3PBA	√	√	(√) chlorpyrifos 3-BPA F-BPA	√	√	√	√
Pesticides (Glyphosate/AMPA) in urine	√	-	(√) Glyphosate, AMPA	√	√	(√) Glyphosate, AMPA	(√) AMPA	√	-	√
Acrylamide (AAMA/GAMA) in urine	√	√	√	√	-	√	(√) AAMA, GAMA	-	-	-

√ = new analysis, - = no analysis, (√) = data already available no new analyses planned

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Table 9: Studies implementing second set priority chemicals in teenagers

TEENAGERS								
	North		East	South		West		
	NEBII	Riksmaten ungdom 2016-17	POLAES	SLO CRP	BEA	ESTEBAN	FLEHS IV	GerES V
	Norway	Sweden	Poland	Slovenia	Spain	France	Belgium	Germany
	NIPH	NFA	NIOM	JSI	ISCI	ANSP	VITO/PIH	UBA
	184	300	281	97	300	300	300	300
Arsenic in urine	-	√	-	(√) Total arsenic, Arsenic III, Arsenic V, MMA, DMA	√	(√) Total arsenic, Arsenic III, Arsenic V, MMA, DMA	(√) Total arsenic, Arsenic III, Arsenic V, MMA, DMA	(√) Total arsenic, Arsenic III, Arsenic V, MMA, DMA, As-B
UV-filters in urine	(√) Bp-3	√	√ (only 4mL)	-	√	√	-	(√) BP 1, BP-3

√ = new analysis, - = no analysis, (√) = data already available no new analyses planned

Table 10: Studies implementing second set priority chemicals in adults

ADULTS									
	North		East		West				Israel
	CPHMINIPUB (parents)	Diet_HBM	POLAES	INSEF-ExQAP	ESTEBAN	HBM4EU-study for Switzerland	ESB	Oriscav-Lux2	RAV MABAT
	Denmark	Iceland	Poland	Portugal	France	Switzerland	Germany	Luxembourg	Israel
	RegionH	UI	NIOM	INSA	ANSP	SWISS TPH	UBA	LNS	MOH-IL
	242+72	200	228	300	300	300	300	210	187
UV-filters in urine	√	-	-	√	√	-	(√) BP 1, BP3	√	-
Mycotoxins (Deoxynivalenol (total)) in urine	-	√	√ (only 4mL)	√	√	-	-	√	-
Acrylamide (AAMA/GAMA) in urine	-	√	√ (only 4mL)	√	√	-	√	√	-
Pesticides (chlorpyrifos/Pyrethroids) in urine	-	-	-	-	-	√	-	-	√
Pesticides (Glyphosate/AMPA) in urine	-	-	-	-	-	√	-	-	-

√ = new analysis, - = no analysis, (√) = data already available no new analyses planned

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Interpretation and communication of results for the 1st and 2nd set of priority substances will be completed by ANSP, UBA, SZU, NIOM, SDU, AUTH, ISCIII, MU, UI, CIPH, RegionH, Swiss TPH, PIH, INSA, IRAS, THL, EPIUD, NFA, JSI, LNS, VITO, MOH-IL, MOH-CY, RIVM. The public communication of results from the aligned studies on EU level must follow the *Strategy for making new HBM4EU results available from the aligned studies* as developed under HBM4EU. According to this strategy data owners of the aligned studies must be involved in the process. The knowledge hub of WP2 collaborates with T8.1 in the development of targeted communication products of the results from the aligned studies.

3.2.2 WP9: Work Package Leader: ISCIII

Task 9.5A Analytical phase

The aligned studies (NIPH, NFA, UI, RegionH, NIOM, EPIUD, JSI, ISCIII, INSA, UBA, LNS, SWISS TPH, ANSP, VITO, PIH, RIVM, MOH-IL, MOH-CY) implementing new analysis of 2nd set priority chemicals will select an HBM4EU approved expert lab to carry out the analysis as detailed in Table , Table and Table . The aligned studies sharing data previously analysed in non HBM4EU expert labs will engage in a-posteriori quality control of the analysis organised by WP9.

3.2.3 WP10: Work Package Leader: VITO

Task 10.3A: Development of statistical analysis plans and coordination of analysis

VITO will coordinate the update of the statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8 (D10.12) by M50. The statistical analysis plan will be developed in close collaboration with the other partners from the statistical working group (UBA, ANSP, ISGLOBAL), researchers from the 2nd set substance groups (ANSP, MU, MUW, UBA, INSA, KI, ISGLOBAL, SDU, VITO) and CGLs 2nd set.

Task 10.4A: Data analysis including the generation of European reference values (RVs)

Statistical analyses will be initiated for the newly generated data of 2nd set substances for the aligned studies of Task 8.1 according to the statistical analysis plan (D10.12) developed by the statistical working group in task 10.3. VITO in collaboration with UBA and ANSP, the respective substance leads (VITO, ANSP, INSA, ISGLOBAL, KI, MUW, RIVM) and WP5 partners will calculate European exposure ranges, analyse geographical comparisons, and compare exposure levels with health-based guidance values (in collaboration with WP5). The research question on exposure determinants is divided as follows between the selected substance groups: acrylamide (KI, MUW), arsenic (VITO), mycotoxins (INSA), pesticides (SDU, VITO, ANSP, RIVM), and UV filters (ISGlobal). Moreover, for the pesticides measured in the Dutch SPECIMEn cohort, analyses will be done comparing the results of the targeted measurements to the results of the suspect screening (in collaboration with WP15) (RIVM). The CGLs 2nd set substances will serve a reviewing role. These statistical analyses will be guided by the statistical working group (VITO, UBA, ANSP, ISGlobal).

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Task 10.6A: Integrating co-funded data into HBM4EU repository and IPCHEM

EEA will continue the work with partners of co-funded studies to bring in and integrate metadata and aggregated (pseudonymous individual data only when legally allowed) co-funded HBM data for the 1st set and 2nd set of priority substances into IPCHEM. The work of 10.6 will focus on the following co-funded data:

- Exposure data from the aligned studies (Task 8.1) from the 2nd set of priority substances and accompanying variables (harmonised individual data) into the data platform established by VITO (Task 10.1) and, if legally allowed, into IPCHEM. Partners foreseen for the 2nd set of priority substances: ANSP, EPIUD, INSA, ISCIII, JSI, MOH-CY, MOH-IL, MU, NIOM, NIPH, SWISS TPH, UBA, VITO, RegionH, NFA, LNS, UI, RIVM. This activity was foreseen and budgeted in 2020 (see AWP2020), but as chemical analyses were delayed, this activity will be continued in 2021 if not yet finalised (budget foreseen in 2020 will be transferred to 2021).

3.2.4 WP14: Work Package Leader: UGR

Task 14.2 Implementation of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of prioritised chemicals in the aligned studies

The selection of the best effect markers relevant for the 2nd set of prioritised substances are again based on the result of the literature searches conducted inside WP14 (D14.5+14.6: the inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances). Four chemical families from the 2nd set have been prioritised for the implementation of effect biomarkers: arsenic, pesticides (glyphosate, pyrethroids and chlorpyrifos), UV-filters (benzophenone-3) and acrylamide. **Importantly**, the implementation of the selected effect biomarkers for the second set priority chemicals will involve the use of effect biomarker measurements and health outcome data already previously collected (**no new fieldwork will be undertaken**). The feasibility of exposure-effect association analyses will therefore depend on the availability of such data among the cohorts that will generate or share exposure biomarker data for the 2nd set of prioritised substances.

For arsenic measured in teenagers, we will focus on neurodevelopment and cardiometabolic health (i.e. steroid and thyroid hormones, urinary 8OHdG, classic metabolic parameters, adipokines and the H3K4me3 occupancy at promoters of blood nuclear receptors including ER, AR, TRs). For pesticides assessed in children, we will focus on neurodevelopment, cardiometabolic and respiratory health (i.e. BDNF at different biological levels, thyroid hormones, insulin resistance parameters and epigenetic markers in blood). For acrylamide assessed in children, we will also focus on neurodevelopment (i.e. BDNF at different biological levels and steroid and thyroid hormones, and H3K4me3 occupancy at promoters of estrogenic and thyroid receptors). Finally, reproductive and thyroid effects will be evaluated for benzophenone-3 exposure in teenagers (i.e. reproductive and thyroid hormones, and H3K4me3 occupancy at promoters of estrogenic and thyroid receptors). UGR and VITO will coordinate, implement and evaluate, those classic and novel effect biomarkers related to the 2nd set of chemicals, in collaboration with INSERM, CNRS, MU, Swiss TPH, ISCIII and NIPH.

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4 References

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5 Appendix

List of DM presented and accepted related to implementation of 2nd set priority chemicals and effect biomarkers in the aligned studies:

- HBM4EU_DM_item10_WP8_Second_priority_substances_aligned_studies
 - MB meeting on 25/01/2019
- HBM4EU_DM_item6_WP8_Implementation_UV-filters_aligned_studies_v1.1
 - MB meeting on 06/05/2019 - **NOT APPROVED**
- HBM4EU_DM_item7_Implementation_biomarkers-of-effect_aligned-studies
 - MB meeting on 06/05/2019 - **NOT APPROVED ADAPTATIONS REQUESTED**
- HBM4EU_DM_item14_WP8_Implementation_UV-filters_aligned_studies_SPEC
 - MB meeting on 05/09/2019
- HBM4EU_DM_item13_WP8_Implementation_mycotoxins_aligned_studies
 - MB meeting on 05/09/2019
- HBM4EU_DM_item6_WP8_Implementation_Acrylamide_aligned_studies_v2.0
 - MB meeting on 14-15/11/2019
- HBM4EU_DM_item7_WP8_WP10_WP14_Effect_markers_v2.0
 - MB meeting on 14-15/11/2019
- HBM4EU_DM_item5_WP8_Alignment_of_studies_inclusion_Israel
- MB meeting on 30/01/2020
- HBM4EU_DM_item14_WP8_Aligned_studies_1st_and_2nd_priority_substances_RIVM_UPD ATE
 - MB meeting on 24-26/06/2020